

AI-Powered Digital Twin Framework for Windstorm Emergency Management in Interconnected Critical Infrastructures

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Introduction

- Extreme windstorms can cause severe damage to physical assets (e.g., overhead lines, trees) and trigger cascading failures across interconnected infrastructures.
- Interdependencies among power, telecommunication, and transportation systems amplify the disruption and societal impact.
- Traditional approaches rely on static, historical data, limiting preparedness; AI enables scalable analysis of complex cascading risks.

Image Source: <http://dx.doi.org/10.13189/ujeee.2019.060304>

Objectives

Develop an AI-powered Digital Twin (DT) framework for windstorm emergency management.

Integrate physics-based windstorm simulation with cascading impact analysis in a unified digital environment.

Use Generative AI (GenAI) as a post-simulation analytical layer for vulnerability and risk analysis.

Support decision-making through stress-testing, risk identification, and response planning under future windstorm scenarios.

AI-Powered Digital Twin Framework

Case Study Application on Cyprus Critical Infrastructure System

Failure/Blockage per Windstorm Scenario

Power Lines failed

Sample Windstorm Impact

Telecom Towers failed

Case Study Application on Cyprus Critical Infrastructure System

GenAI-Based Post-Event Risk Analysis

Most Vulnerable Lines and Their Impact on Average Energy Not Served

- GenAI identifies the most **critical power lines** contributing to high system-level ENS.
- Failure of these lines leads to significant service disruption, quantified via **expected ENS**.
- Strengthening these lines can substantially **reduce ENS** (e.g., Line 38 → 324 MWh saved).

Line	Trials	Avg ENS (failed)	Avg ENS (intact)	ENS saved	
Line 38 #3	5	2460 MWh	2136 MWh	324 MWh	13.2%
Line 6 #4	8	1409 MWh	1266 MWh	143 MWh	10.2%
Line 11 #2	5	2471 MWh	2358 MWh	113 MWh	4.6%
Line 8 #1	7	1793 MWh	1710 MWh	84 MWh	4.7%
Line 16 #5	4	2775 MWh	2763 MWh	12 MWh	0.4%

Trials: number of simulated windstorm scenarios where the line is impacted

Key Findings

- The hybrid physics-AI DT effectively captures complex, nonlinear relationships between wind events and cascading infrastructure failures.
- Enables rapid identification of vulnerable assets and risk hotspots across interconnected infrastructures.
- Supports stress-testing under a wide range of plausible future windstorm scenarios.
- Provides actionable insights through GenAI-driven post-event learning and risk analysis for emergency management.

Conclusion

- This work presents a hybrid physics-based and AI-enhanced Digital Twin framework for windstorm emergency management in interconnected critical infrastructures.
- The framework offers a flexible and extensible foundation to improve resilience to climate-driven hazards and support decision-making across all stages of emergency management.

THANK YOU!

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SPARROW